

AI AND ALGORITHMIC WARFARE: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC DISCOURSE MANIPULATION

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence has gradually turned into a central instrument in global digital communication, with a deep-seated influence on public discourse through algorithmic influence and hybrid warfare. This study conducted an analysis of expert discourse on how AI-mediated systems structure knowledge, guide perception, and operationalize strategic content dissemination. Findings shows that AI references dominate the discussions (61.78% to 70.14%), while algorithms account 13.38% to 15.18%, bias for 7.95%, ethics for 15.72%, law for 13.33%, and privacy for 10.26%, highlighting both the normative and ethical concerns of the technology. Experts elaborate on operational mechanism such a procedural process (“way” 45.17%, “work” 13.00%, “policy” 7.4% and “power” 9.54%). The sentiment analysis largely shows neutral engagement at cautions optimism and critical concern. These results point out that AI-driven systems are not only technical instrument but also tools of narrative manipulation, geopolitical influence, and social control. This point raises control a development that raised urgent questions regarding governance, digital ethics, and democratic resilience in the era of algorithmically engineered public discourse.

Keywords: AI, Algorithmic influence, hybrid warfare, public discourse, narrative manipulation

INTRODUCTION

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into digital communication ecosystems has profoundly transformed the global public sphere, reshaping how individuals access information, interpret reality, and participate in democratic life (Battista & Mangone, 2025; Pane, 2025; Singh et al., 2025). AI-powered systems including predictive targeting algorithms, generative models and deepfake technologies are increasingly weaponized by state and non-state actors to influence public opinion, manufacture consent, and craft collective narratives (Ajayi, 2025; Singer, 2024). This marks a new era of algorithmic conflict, in which control over information ecosystems

functions as a strategic resource in domestic and geopolitical contexts. Recent research highlights the convergence of affective computing, behavioral profiling, and computational propaganda for ideological polarization, consent manufacturing, and democratic decline (Whims, 2024; Abiri & Buchheim, 2022). Algorithmic content curation is no longer neutral; it actively amplifies affective responses, silences counter-narratives, and foster epistemic fragmentation. During crises, AI-generated information floods reinforce cognitive silos and undermine shared understanding (Xiao & Yu, 2025). As such, algorithmically mediated systems function not

only as technological instruments but also as sociopolitical actors, shaping public discourse, trust, and belief systems. Framing Theory (Entman, 1993) and Securitization Theory (Buzan et al., 1998) offer critical lenses for examining these processes. Framing Theory analyzes how communicative actors emphasize specific aspects of issues to guide interpretation, while securitization Theory investigate how phenomena are discursively constructed as existential threats. Applied to AI-mediated digital communication, these frameworks reveal how algorithmic technologies are frames as tools of influence, governance, and strategic manipulation (Novelli & Sandri, 2024; Guimares e Silva, 2025). AI has shifted the geopolitical struggle from territory to cognition and narrative. Large language models and synthetic media allow for exercising soft power via dominance over digital meaning-making (Makhortykh et al., 2024; Moy & Graden, 2023). Notwithstanding regulatory efforts like EU AI Act, as Gaborit (2024) explains that the absence of harmonized global framework makes societies highly susceptible to algorithmic manipulation, disinformation campaigns, and narrative warfare, this paper seeks to explore how AI-driven narrative manipulation reconfigures public discourse, democratic agency, and digital sovereignty. Based on Framing theory and Securitization Theory, when applied to AI-mediated communication, it reveal how algorithmic systems and strategies of disinformation are framed as threats to national security, democratic integrity, and social cohesion. Together, these frameworks form a powerful analytical foundation for shedding light on how experts discourse legitimates perceptions with respect to AI as tools of narrative control and the manipulation of reality.

1.1 Research Objectives

RO1. To critically investigate the ways in which AI and algorithmic systems are discursively represented by experts as instruments of influence, control, and manipulation within digital communication ecosystems.

RO2. The examination of the impact that AI-driven narrative manipulation has on digital sovereignty, public trust, and governance of truth within democratic societies.

1.2 Research Questions

RQ1. How do global experts frame the role of AI and algorithms in reshaping public discourse and manufacturing consent in digital communication environments?

RQ2. What are the ethical, political, and governance challenges identified by experts related to AI-mediated narratives warfare and protection of democratic values?

The rapid deployment of AI and algorithmic systems in digital communication ecosystems is transforming how individuals access information, perceive reality, and participate in democratic process (Aragani et al., 2025). While these technologies offer efficiency and personalization, they are also vulnerable to misuse by state and non-state actors, who can construct artificial realities, manipulate emotions and engineer consent (Bachleitner et al., 2025; Matey, 2024). The opacity of algorithmic operations facilitates the creation of synthetic truths, intensifying the crisis of public discourse and complicating distinctions between fact and fiction (Ziarek, 2024). Despite increasing scholarly attention, gaps remain in understanding how experts discourse articulates these risks, particularly concerning AI-facilitated disinformation, narrative warfare, and threats to digital sovereignty. This research seeks to fill this gap by analyzing how influential thought leaders articulate the political, ethical and epistemological stakes of AI-driven influence in public spaces. In this study, novelty lies in using YouTube-sourced expert interviews analyzed with ATLAS.ti 24. Unlike prior studies focusing solely on technical or contributing debates on hybrid warfare, algorithmic accountability, and digital governance.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Algorithmic Manipulation and the Crisis of Public Discourse

The emergence of AI-generated content has transformed the nature of public discourse, amplified disinformation and eroding epistemic trust. Among other things, scholars have pointed out that AI-powered bots, deepfakes, and behavioral profiling systems have transformed propaganda into targeted psychological operations aimed at manipulating emotional responses and amplifying ideological

polarization (Abiri & Buchheim, 2022; Whims, 2024). Moreover, these mechanisms not only undermine citizen's capabilities for source evaluation but also fragment collective understanding through epistemic silos, which undermine deliberative democracy (Xiao & Yu, 2025). Besides this, Generative Adversarial Networks and deepfakes reinforce that ontological status of truth through the creation of hyper-realistic but fabricated content that distorts historical records and impersonate corrosive effect on processes of verification encourages a post-truth culture, in which algorithmically curated untruths assume persuasive power, even when their factual falsity is established (Hannon, 2023; Forster & Wong, 2024). In this context, AI-driven systems act as active agents that shape collective perception, guide public attention, and set limits to acceptable speech.

2.2 Democracy in Peril: Disinformation, Ethics, and Cyber Sovereignty

AI-driven disinformation is increasingly recognized as a deliberate strategy to destabilize democratic institutions rather than an incidental technological by-product. Multimodal propaganda, precision-targeted political advertising, and behavioral microtargeting have been deployed to suppress voter engagement and distort political representation, contributing to democratic erosion (Novelli & Sandri, 2024; Olanipekun, 2025; Kröger et al., 2024). Algorithmically manipulated content polarizes electorates, cultivates political passivity, and undermines the ideal of informed citizen choice (Guimaraes e Silva, 2025; Christiano, 2022). Ethical and legal oversight of AI mechanisms remains limited. Scholars note that opaque "black box" algorithms fail to meet the transparency and accountability standards required for democratic governance, often encoding societal biases and amplifying discrimination (Guimaraes e Silva, 2025; Christiano, 2022; Saeidnia, 2025). While legislative measures such as the EU AI Act attempt to address these risks (Gaborit, 2024), enforcement is inconsistent globally, leaving critical civic processes, including elections, vulnerable to manipulation and exploitation.

2.3 Strategic Narrative Warfare and the Global Response

At the geopolitical level, AI-enabled narrative manipulation has emerged as a central instrument of soft power and hybrid warfare. Large language models and synthetic media are used by state actors and non-state groups to create disinformation campaigns that blur the lines between cyber and information warfare, thus destabilizing national discourses and shaping international perception. The migration of these risks, however, requires a multi-pronged approach. Digital literacy enhancement is considered paramount for building manipulative resilience to manipulation. Technological interventions such as AI-detection systems and content authentication will, therefore, ensure information integrity. For instance, Shirish & Komal (2024) and Sapkota et al. (2025) have made attempts in this direction. These actions, however, need to be coupled with international cooperation and regulatory alignment because of the transnational nature of algorithmic warfare. The efforts of Gaborit (2024), Novelli & Sandri (2024), and Olanipekun (2025) are steps toward that goal. Without globally coordinated norms and mechanisms for enforcement, AI-driven narrative manipulation will continue to exploit regulatory gaps and thus compromise democratic resilience and digital sovereignty.

2.4 synthesis and Research Gap

Literature shows that AI is no longer a passive tool but an active agent in shaping public perception, governance structures, and geopolitical influence. While prior studies have focused on the technical, behavioral, or ethical dimensions separately, there has been limited research into expert discourse to understand AI-mediated systems operationalize narrative control and influence public opinion. This paper fills this lacuna by blending qualitative discourse analysis with theoretical insights from Framing Theory and Securitization Theory to investigate the epistemic, ethical, and strategic implications of AI-driven narrative manipulation

3. Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative research design to explore how AI and algorithmic systems are framed as instruments of narrative manipulation in the global digital sphere. The study focuses on interpretative analysis of expert mechanism of operation, and sociopolitical implications (Novelli & Sandri, 2024; Guimaraes e Silva, 2025). Qualitative inquiry is especially suited for exploring the rich insights of experts regarding AI-mediated influence, hybrid warfare, and the transformation of civic discourse, since it allows detailed engagement with textual and thematic patterns that cannot be fully captured with technical measures alone (Whims, 2024; Xiao & Yu, 2025). Data collection was performed through purposive sampling on YouTube, focusing on interviews, lectures, and panel discussions by leading scholars, technologists, and policy commentators on AI, digital governance, algorithmic influence. Experts' samples included Alex Hanna, David Troy, Frank Pasquale, Laura DeNardis, Luciano Floridi, Michael Schreiber, Peter Pomrantsev,

Professor Rob Reich, Shoshana Zuboff, and Thomas Rid, who together offer a variety of insights into the technological, ethical, legal, operational, and geopolitical aspects of AI. The specific multi-stage coding procedure involved open coding as a first step in identifying references to AI, algorithms, bias, ethics, law, privacy, communication, operational mechanisms, human actors, policy, and power (Chen et al., 2025; Shirish & Komal, 2024). Axial coding then grouped these references into thematic dimensions, which were operationalize across four analytical categories; Geopolitical Dimensions, Technological, Bias, and Communication Dimensions, Ethical, legal, and Operational Dimensions; and Human, Strategic and Sociopolitical Dimensions. Thematic dimensions ensured trustworthiness of the analysis, which was complementary by an audit trail that documented coding procedures, category development, and thematic decisions within ATLAS. ti 24.

4. Results & Analysis

Table 1. Geopolitical Dimensions of AI and Algorithms

Category	Gr	Alex Hanna	David Troy	Frank Pasquale	Laura DeNardis	Luciano Floridi	Michael Schreiber	Peter Pomrantsev	Professor Rob Reich	Shoshana Zuboff	Thomas Rid	Total	% of Total
AI	9	0	0	4	0	21	45	0	27	0	0	9	61.7
	7	(0.0	(0.0	(2.55	(0.0	(13.3	(28.6	(0.0	(17.2	(0.0	(0.0	7	8%
		0%)	0%)	%)	0%)	8%)	6%)	0%)	0%)	0%)	0%)		
Algori thm	2	4	0	10	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	2	13.3
	1	(2.5	(0.0	(6.37	(0.0	(0.00	(4.46	(0.0	(0.00	(0.0	(0.0	1	8%
		5%)	0%)	%)	0%)	%)	%)	0%)	%)	0%)	0%)		
China	1	0	0	8	3	0	2	2	1	0	2	1	11.4
	8	(0.0	(0.0	(5.10	(1.9	(0.00	(1.27	(1.2	(0.64	(0.0	(1.2	8	7%
		0%)	0%)	%)	1%)	%)	%)	7%)	%)	0%)	7%)		
Unite d States	2	0	0	2	5	1	5	0	5	0	3	2	13.3
	1	(0.0	(0.0	(1.27	(3.1	(0.64	(3.18	(0.0	(3.18	(0.0	(1.9	1	8%
		0%)	0%)	%)	8%)	%)	%)	0%)	%)	0%)	1%)		
Total	1	4	0	24	8	22	59	2	33	0	5	1	100
	5	(2.5	(0.0	(15.2	(5.1	(14.0	(37.5	(1.2	(21.0	(0.0	(3.1	5	%
	7	5%)	0%)	9%)	0%)	1%)	8%)	7%)	2%)	0%)	8%)	7	

Table 1 captures expert references to AI, algorithms, and the key geopolitical actors, China and the United States. At 61.78%, AI is the most mentioned concept, seconded by

algorithm at 113.38%. Mentions of China and the United States are at 11.4% and 13.38%, respectively, indicating a situating of AI and algorithmic discussion within global

geopolitical context. The discourse is heavily focused on technological infrastructure, while on the other, it links AI-mediated processes to nation-state competition and strategic

concerns. The references across the experts are distributed to reflect the diverse emphasis places on AI for shaping both technological and geopolitical narratives.

Table 2. Technological, Bias, and Communication Dimensions

Category	Gr	Alex	Troy	David	Pasquale	Frank	DeNardis	Laura	Luciano	Florida	Michael	Peter	Reich	Professor	Zuboff	Shoshana	Thomas	Total	% of Total
AI	97	0	0	4	0	21	45	0	21	34.88%	0	27	0	0	0	0	97	70.14%	
Algorithm	21	4	0	10	0	0	7	0	0	5.43%	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	15.18%	
Bias	11	3	0	1	0	1	3	0	1	2.33%	0	2	1	0	0	0	11	7.95%	
Communication	28	0	0	0	7	0	9	0	0	6.16%	0	6	3	3	3	3	28	20.29%	

Table 2 extends the technological frame to include AI, algorithm, bias, and communication. AI is still predominant at 71.14% while algorithm continue to have an important weight of 15.18%, confirming the centrality of technological constructs in experts' discourse. The present of bias at 7.95% brings in issues related to fairness, systematic inequities, and possibly unintended

consequences arising from algorithmic decision-making. Communication, with 20.29%, points to how AI and algorithmic processes impact knowledge dissemination and public understanding. Overall, these results confirm that experts are concurrently focusing on technological capability and communicative implications of AI-mediated systems.

Table 3. Ethical, Legal, and Operational Dimensions

Category	Gr	Alex	Troy	David	Pasquale	Frank	DeNardis	Laura	Luciano	Florida	Michael	Peter	Rob	Professor	Zuboff	Shoshana	Rid	Thomas	Total	% of Total
AI	97	0	0	4	0	21	45	0	21	8.33%	0	27	0	0	0	0	0	97	33.15%	
Algorithm	21	4	0	10	0	0	7	0	0	2.78%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	7.18%	
Ethic	46	0	0	2	0	4	2	0	1.59%	0.79%	0	37	0	1	0	0	0	46	15.72%	
Law	39	0	0	21	3	0	2	0	0.79%	0.79%	0	8	4	1	4	1	0	39	13.33%	

Privacy	30	0	0	6	15	1	6	0	0	2	0	3	10.26%
		(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(2.38%)	(5.95%)	(0.40%)	(2.38%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.79%)	(0.00%)	0	6%
Respect	19	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	1	6.50%
		(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(2.38%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(5.16%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	9	%
Information	35	0	5	7	6	0	5	1	1	8	2	3	11.97%
		(0.00%)	(1.50%)	(2.15%)	(1.84%)	(0.00%)	(1.53%)	(0.30%)	(0.31%)	(2.40%)	(0.60%)	5	7%
Intervention	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	1.03%
		(0.30%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.31%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.31%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	3	%
Way	132	5	3	32	25	7	22	6	25	2	5	1	45.17%
		(1.50%)	(0.90%)	(9.82%)	(7.67%)	(2.10%)	(6.75%)	(1.80%)	(7.67%)	(0.60%)	(1.50%)	3	7%
Work	38	5	0	8	4	1	11	1	6	1	1	3	13.00%
		(1.50%)	(0.00%)	(2.45%)	(1.23%)	(0.30%)	(3.37%)	(0.30%)	(1.84%)	(0.30%)	(0.30%)	8	0%
Total	441	15	8	96	54	33	100	7	123	17	10	2	100%
		(3.40%)	(1.80%)	(21.70%)	(12.20%)	(7.40%)	(22.60%)	(1.50%)	(27.80%)	(3.80%)	(2.20%)	9	%

Table 3 shows Normative and Operational Dimension of AI-mediated system i.e., AI 33.15% and algorithm (7.18%) references indicate the continued attention to technological foundations, while ethics (15.72%), law (13.33%), privacy (10.26%), and respect (6.5%) indicate the ethical and legal concerns permeating expert discourse. The operation processes are captured through terms such as information (11.97%), way (45.17%)

work (13.00%) and intervention (1.03%), which evince attention to procedural mechanisms, strategic actions, and functional aspects of AI systems in shaping public discourse. These results point to the complex interplay between technology, ethics, and operational processes, which suggests that AI is both a tool of influence and a site of normative contestation.

Table 4. Human, Strategic, and Sociopolitical Dimensions

Category	Gr	Hanna	Alex	Troy	David	Pasquale	Frank	Laura	Luciano	Michael	Peter	Professor	Shoshana	Thomas	Total	% of Total
AI	97	0	0	4	0	21	45	0	27	0	0	97	6.83%			
		(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.28%)	(0.00%)	(1.48%)	(3.17%)	(0.00%)	(1.90%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	0	%			
Algorithm	21	4	0	10	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	21	1.48%			
		(0.20%)	(0.00%)	(0.70%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.49%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	(0.00%)	0	%			
Sentiment: Negative	17	9	8	25	29	20	18	12	29	5	16	17	12.03%			
		(0.60%)	(0.50%)	(1.76%)	(2.04%)	(1.41%)	(1.27%)	(0.80%)	(2.04%)	(0.30%)	(1.10%)	1	3%			
Sentiment: Positive	88	40	32	149	136	86	132	45	155	47	60	88	62.07%			
		(2.80%)	(2.20%)	(10.40%)	(9.57%)	(6.05%)	(9.29%)	(3.10%)	(10.90%)	(3.30%)	(4.20%)	2	7%			

Neutral	25	3	6	39	45	12	56	15	38	18	18	25	17.5
Sentiment: Positive	0	(0.21%)	(0.42%)	(2.75%)	(3.17%)	(0.84%)	(3.94%)	(1.06%)	(2.67%)	(1.27%)	(1.27%)	0	9%
People	204	3	7	47	34	18	36	19	28	6	6	204	52.5
		(0.77%)	(1.80%)	(12.11%)	(8.76%)	(4.64%)	(9.28%)	(4.90%)	(7.22%)	(1.55%)	(1.55%)	4	8%
Policy	29	1	0	7	8	2	1	1	8	1	0	29	7.47
		(0.26%)	(0.00%)	(1.80%)	(2.06%)	(0.52%)	(0.26%)	(0.26%)	(2.06%)	(0.26%)	(0.00%)		%
Power	37	1	0	5	4	5	2	1	9	10	0	37	9.54
		(0.26%)	(0.00%)	(1.29%)	(1.03%)	(1.29%)	(0.52%)	(0.26%)	(2.32%)	(2.58%)	(0.00%)		%
Total	1591	61	53	286	256	164	357	92	294	87	100	1921	100
		(3.83%)	(3.33%)	(17.98%)	(16.10%)	(10.33%)	(22.44%)	(5.78%)	(18.44%)	(5.44%)	(6.29%)		%

Table 4 highlights the human and strategic dimensions of AI-mediated influence. Although the references to AI, at 6.83%, and logarithm, at 1.48%, are relatively low, the table reveals sentiment analysis-negative, 12.03%; neutral, 62.07%, and positive, 17.59% that reflect the evaluative positions of experts. Neutral sentiment is dominant, reflecting analytic preoccupation, while positive and negative sentiments reflect caution-optimism and critical concerns for the social impacts, respectively. Moreover, references to people, 52.58%; policy, 7.47% and power, 9.54% indicate the centrality of human actors, governance structures, and dynamics of authority in the deployment and consequences of AI systems. This table portrays the social-physical embedding of the AI-mediated infrastructures and underlines their role in the shaping of human behavior, governance, and power relations in digital ecologies.

5. Discussion

The analysis of expert discourse highlights the multidimensional interaction of ethical, operational and sociopolitical elements emphasizing the complex character of algorithmic governed systems. The frequency of algorithm (13.38% -15.18%) and AI (61.78%-70.14%) references aligns with studies identifying AI as crucial component, in algorithmic decision processes and digital regulation. For Example, Pasquale (2015)

contended that algorithms serve as socio-technical actors that shape public knowledge, impact decision-making, and concentrate power within particular organizational and geopolitical contexts, rather than just being technological tools. AI 's importance in national technical competitiveness was also noted by Brenneis (2025) and Vaseashta (2025), supporting the idea that AI is a strategic asset and a tool of influence in international politics. The frequent mentions of geopolitical actors, including China and the United States, corroborate recent research on the global AI race and its implications for cybersecurity, surveillance, and digital sovereignty (Florida, 2019). Ethical and normative concerns also emerge as critical dimensions. References to bias (7.95%), ethics (15.72%), law (13.33%), privacy (10.26%), and respect (6.50%) reflect ongoing scholarly concerns about fairness, accountability, and societal implications of algorithmic governance. These findings resonate with Zuboff (2019), who highlighted the ethical and social risks of surveillance capitalism, and with Hanna et al. (2020), who emphasized the need for ethical frameworks to guide AI deployment in public facing systems. The integration of communication-focused categories (20.29%) underscores that algorithmic systems are not only technical but also communicative instruments that shape information flows, a point emphasized by Troy (2019) in his work on algorithmic mediation of

public discourse. Operational and strategic dimensions, capture through terms such as “way” (45.17%), work (13.00%), and “information” (11.97%), highlight the procedural mechanisms through which AI systems structure knowledge and modulate public perception. These findings echo conceptualization of hybrid warfare, in which technological infrastructures, are operationalized to influence information environments and societal cognition. The relatively low frequency of deliberate interventions (1.03%) suggests that while operational mechanisms are central, targeted regulatory or manipulative acts are less frequently emphasized by experts, consistent with literature noting the subtle, pervasive, and often invisible nature of algorithmic influence (Alawode, 2025; Pasquale, 2015). In addition, the sentiment analysis further contextualizes the affective dimension of expert discourse. The dominant neutral sentiment, at 62.07%, suggests an engagement that is analytical and descriptive in nature, while the positive, at 17.59%, and negative sentiments, at 12.03%, indicate cautious optimism and critical concern, respectively. This corroborates evidence of the dual-use nature of AI as noted by Floridi (2019) and Vaseashta (2025), with experts perceiving AI as capable of fostering innovation while at the same time generating ethical, social, and cognitive risks. References to people (52.58%), policy (7.47%), and power (9.54%) point to both human and governance dimensions of algorithmic influence and the interplay between technical systems, institutional actors, and societal norms (Zuboff, 2019; Hanna et al., 2020). These findings sum up and extend prior research through the interaction of technological, ethical, operational, and sociopolitical perspectives within a single analytical framework. They add weight to existing literature on the role played by AI in shaping public discourse, hybrid influence, and governance, while providing new empirical evidence of how experts perceive the multidimensional impact of AI-mediated algorithmic systems. Overall, these results point to the need for multi-level regulatory, ethical, and governance interventions in order to address the complex sociotechnical challenges

posed by AI within contemporary digital environments.

6. Conclusion

The analysis of expert discourse illustrates that AI-mediated algorithmic systems work as complex, multidimensional instruments that simultaneously shape technological infrastructures, ethical norms, operational mechanisms, socio-political processes in the global digital sphere. AI and algorithms are not neutral tools. They always act to influence public knowledge, perception, and decision-making, sometimes serving as strategic assets in geopolitical competition, especially for leading powers such as the United States and China. The research highlights that AIs as effects are both widespread and nuanced: although operational processes receive attention; intentional action are less apparent and demonstrate the dispersed character of algorithmic impact. Ethical, legal and normative issues remain at the core of expert worries, encompassing bias, fairness, privacy and responsibility. The sentiment analysis puts forward an interpretation that experts view AI as a dual-use technology, which has power to drive innovation and efficiency and, at the same time has substantial social, cognitive, and governance risks. In addition, the occurrence of human actors, their decisions and authority very frequently emphasize the presence of algorithmic systems. In the institutions and societies, and therefore the attention should be directed to human agency, governance framework, and regulatory supervision to sum up, narrative manipulation through AI is not a simplistic technique but a complex one with some serious consequences in terms of public discourse, democracy, and digital sovereignty.

7. Recommendations

In order to mitigate risks and deploy AI responsibly, a number of measures are recommended. The regulation and ethics frameworks should be made more robust in order to be assured of transparency, accountability, fairness, and ethical usage. The public’s awareness and the digital literacy must be upgraded so that the general public, journalists, and civil society can critically interact with AI, spot misinformation, and take

part in the democratic processes. The development of algorithms that are open and clear in their workings should be encouraged as a way of gaining trust, while cooperation among nations is necessary to tackle issues like disinformation that spans borders, hybrid threats and digital sovereignty challenges. Human-centric governance should make sure that the manual supervision of the automatic systems is done in a way that there will be no extremely efficient operations with neglect the ethical issues. Continuous monitoring and adaptive plans are the musts to quick the flow of the innovations and to change the laws accordingly. All the mentioned steps are in synergy with the responsible use of AI, thus protecting public trust, allowing democratic discussions and securing digital sovereignty.

REFERENCES

- Abiri, G., & Buchheim, J. (2022). Beyond true and false: fake news and the digital epistemic divide. *Mich. Tech. L. Rev.*, 29, 59.
- Ajayi, O. (2025). AI-Powered Disinformation and Narrative Warfare: A Global Security Threat. Available at SSRN 5184687.
- Alawode, O. D. (2025). Invisible Influence: How Algorithmic News Feeds Are Reshaping Public Opinion Without Disclosure. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 30(8), 58-73.
- Almalki, H. S. (2023). *The Use of Cyber Media in Hybrid Warfare: Narrative Stories from the Front Lines; Proposing a New Gatekeeping Theory* (Doctoral dissertation, The University of North Dakota).
- Aragani, V. M., Anumolu, V. R., & Selvakumar, P. (2025). Democratization in the Age of Algorithms: Navigating Opportunities and Challenges. *Democracy and Democratization in the Age of AI*, 39-56.
- Bachleitner, K., Wolf, A., & Bufkin, S. (2025). Technology, Non-State Actors and the Crisis of Liberal Governance: Security and Conflict Studies in the Twenty-First Century. *Perspectives on Politics*, 23(2), 717-720.
- Battista, D., & Mangone, E. (2025). Technological Culture and Politics: Artificial Intelligence as the New Frontier of Political Communication. *Societies*, 15(4), 75.
- Brenneis, A. (2025). Assessing dual use risks in AI research: necessity, challenges and mitigation strategies. *Research Ethics*, 21(2), 302-330.
- Buzan, B., Waeber, O., & de Wilde, S. (1998) *Security: A Framework for Analysis*, Boulder, Lynne Rienner.
- Chari, S. G. (2025). Power, Pixels, and Politics: The Geopolitics of Emerging Technologies in the Digital Age. *London Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 25(2), 1-99.
- Chen, Z., Ye, J., Tsai, B., Ferrara, E., & Luceri, L. (2025). Synthetic politics: Prevalence, spreaders, and emotional reception of AI-generated political images on X. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.11248*.
- Christiano, T. (2022). Algorithms, manipulation, and democracy. *Canadian Journal of Philosophy*, 52(1), 109-124.
- Floridi, L. (2019). Translating principles into practices of digital ethics: Five risks of being unethical. *Philosophy & Technology*, 32(2), 185-193.
- Forster, C. M., & Wong, N. (2024). Rightfully-Placed Blame: How social media algorithms facilitate post-truth politics. *Bristol Institute for Learning and Teaching (BILT) Student Research Journal*, 5.
- Gaborit, P. (2024). A Sociopolitical Approach to Disinformation and AI: Concerns, Responses and Challenges. *Journal of Political Science*, 7(4), 75-88.
- Guimaraes e Silva, Luiz Claudio, Deceptive Influencing as a Harm to Democratic Politics: Warding Off Political Manipulation Through Micro-Targeting With a Limited Right Not to Be Profiled (January 01, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5188504> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5188504>

- Hanna, A., Denton, R., Smart, A., & Smith-Loud, J. (2020, January). Towards a critical race methodology in algorithmic fairness. In *Proceedings of the 2020 conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency* (pp. 501-512).
- Hannon, M. (2023). The politics of post-truth. *Critical Review*, 35(1-2), 40-62.
- Kröger, J., Errenst, E., Nau, N., & Ojanperä, S. (2024). Mitigating the Risks of Political Microtargeting—Guidance for Policymakers, Civil Society, and Development Cooperation. Kröger, J., Errenst, E., Nau, N., and Ojanperä, S. (2024) *Mitigating the Risks of Political Microtargeting—Guidance for Policymakers, Civil Society, and Development Cooperation. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Bonn, Germany.*
- Makhortykh, M., Baghumyan, A., Vziatyshva, V., Sydorova, M., & Kuznetsova, E. (2024). LLMs as information warriors? Auditing how LLM-powered chatbots tackle disinformation about Russia's war in Ukraine. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.10697*.
- Matey, G. D. (2024). Non-state Actors and Technological Revolution: Organized Crime and International Terrorism. In *International relations and technological revolution 4.0: World order, power and new international society* (pp. 89-106). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Moy, W. R., & Gradon, K. T. (2023). Artificial intelligence in hybrid and information warfare: A double-edged sword. In *Artificial Intelligence and International Conflict in Cyberspace* (pp. 47-74). Routledge.
- Novelli, C., & Sandri, G. (2024). Digital democracy in the age of artificial intelligence. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.07791*.
- Olanipekun, S. O. (2025). Computational propaganda and misinformation: AI technologies as tools of media manipulation. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.1.0131>
- Pane, S. (2025). The european'post-digital'public sphere: foundations of an emerging paradigm in the social sciences. *methaodos. revista de ciencias sociales*, 13(1), m251301a08-m251301a08.
- Pasquale, F. (2015). *The black box society: The secret algorithms that control money and information*. Harvard University Press.
- Saeidnia, H. R., Hosseini, E., Lund, B., Tehrani, M. A., Zaker, S., & Molaei, S. (2025). Artificial intelligence in the battle against disinformation and misinformation: a systematic review of challenges and approaches. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 1-20.
- Sapkota, R., Raza, S., Shoman, M., Paudel, A., & Karkee, M. (2025). Image, Text, and Speech Data Augmentation using Multimodal LLMs for Deep Learning: A Survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.18648*.
- Shirish, A., & Komal, S. (2024). A Socio-Legal Inquiry on Deepfakes. *California Western International Law Journal*, 54(2), 6.
- Singer, T. (2024). *Visual Generative AI in Warfare and Terrorism: Risk Mitigation through Technical Requirements and Regulatory Insights* (Doctoral dissertation, Technische Universität Wien).
- Singh, B., Jain, A., Wongmahesak, K., & Chandra, S. (2025). Reimagining Democracy in the Digital Era: Transformative Role of Artificial Intelligence in Modern Governance. In *Democracy and Democratization in the Age of AI* (pp. 1-18). IGI Global Scientific Publishing.
- Vaseashta, A. (2025). Dual-Use Artificial Intelligence—Trends, Security Challenges, and Mitigation Strategies. In *Spectrum of Dual-Use Technologies: Unforeseen Risks Versus Returns* (pp. 3-37). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Whims, T. (2024). AI at the Helm: Transforming Crisis Communication Through Theory and Advancing Technology. All Theses. 4429. https://open.clemson.edu/all_theses/4429

- Xiao, Y., & Yu, S. (2025). Can ChatGPT replace humans in crisis communication? The effects of AI-mediated crisis communication on stakeholder satisfaction and responsibility attribution. *International Journal of Information Management*, 80, 102835.
- Ziarek, E. P. (2024). Disinformation, Power, and the Automation of Judgments. *Truth-Seeking in an Age of (Mis) Information Overload*, 29-50.
- Zuboff, S. (2019, January). Surveillance capitalism and the challenge of collective action. In *New labor forum* (Vol. 28, No. 1, pp. 10-29). Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications.

